

EXERCISE AS A COMPONENT OF THE CONTENT OF TEACHING BILINGUALISM

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Abstract: This article talks about the exercise as a component of the content of teaching bilingualism, in the broad sense of understanding - relative proficiency in a second language, the ability to use it in certain areas of communication.

Key words: bilingualism, component, polyglot, verbal communication, bilinguals, monolinguals , exercise.

At the present stage of development of society, the main task of the language teaching process is the education of bilinguals , as is common throughout the world. In some countries, bilingualism is, due to current circumstances, a common situation, and when teaching foreign languages, the tasks of training polyglots, people who speak several (more than two) languages, are solved here.

The word "bilingualism" (from the Latin bi - two , lingua - language) means bilingualism. Bilingualism is a person's ability to use two languages and the practical ability to use them in the process of communication. Experts distinguish a narrow and broad understanding of bilingualism: in a narrow sense , it is more or less fluent command of two languages: native and non-native, and in a broad sense, relative proficiency in a second language, the ability to use it in certain areas of communication. From this point of view, the minimum level of proficiency in a second language can be considered a level sufficient for an individual to perform speech actions for communication or obtaining information, during which certain functions of the second language are realized. If language proficiency is below this level, then there is no sufficient reason to consider such proficiency as a sign of bilingualism. Some people admit that they understand foreign speech, but do not dare ("embarrassed") to speak. This level may be sufficient to understand what we are being told . And in the absence of others who could help people in difficult life situations of communicating with foreigners, such a "native speaker" of the language automatically becomes the leader of the team. Complete (sufficient) *bilingualism appears in the form of almost identical proficiency in two languages and their alternate use depending on the conditions of speech communication. From the perspective of psycholinguistics, bilingualism is characterized as the ability to use two language systems for communication.*

According to a number of scientists, there are more bilinguals in the world than monolinguals . About 70% of the world's population speak two or more languages to one degree or another, experts suggest.

Contrary to opposing opinions, it is believed that bilingualism has a positive effect on the development of memory, the ability to understand, analyze and discuss language phenomena. People who speak two languages are distinguished by their intelligence, quick reaction, mathematical skills and logic. Previously, they talked about the negative impact of

bilingualism on a child's development. A child who simultaneously uses two languages will lag behind in speech (and not only) development in both languages, supporters of this position believed. These concerns have been allayed by a number of experimental studies.

Fully developing bilinguals tend to be good students and master abstract science, literature, and other foreign languages better than others.

Bilingual children need language education in the family. If this is not given due attention, namely, the conversation with the child is conducted only in his native language, and outside the home he hears only speech in a non-native language, then a differentiation occurs in the linguistic spheres of communication. In this regard, bilingual children need a clearly structured system of exercises.

A distinctive feature is the plot-based way of organizing exercises in the lesson. The lesson is a single storyline, guided by some event: real (holiday), fictional, game or fairy tale. Each lesson, in turn, represents a link in the storyline of the entire course of learning.

The most important feature of the Russian language lesson is the strict **dependence of the exercises on the goal**. As you know, the goal determines the means, so exercises as a means of learning must be adequate to the goal. What does it mean?

The adequacy of exercises is their potential ability, due to a certain nature and qualities, to serve as the most effective means of achieving a specific goal.

There is also the problem of matching the exercise to the nature of the skill being developed - lexical, grammatical, pronunciation, spelling, etc. Each of them is specific, which means that in each case those exercises should be used that take into account the specifics of the skill and form the actions that make up this skill.

In addition, it is necessary to take into account the learning conditions. We will show how difficult it is to determine the adequacy of exercises and what a teacher can do to guide this.

Let's say the goal of the lesson is to develop grammatical speaking skills (using the future tense), and as a means we are offered a stand-in table of the usual type. We will reason as follows.

Among the qualities of a speech skill (including grammatical skills), the main ones are: automation, stability, flexibility, etc. Are the actions performed by the student when performing substitution tables capable of forming these qualities? What actions does he perform?

1. Constructs sentences.
2. Constructs a lot of them (and quickly).
3. Constructs similar sentences.
4. Directs attention to the content of sentences (at best), because there is no speech task.

Since there is no situationality, the conclusion is legitimate that the quality of automation can be developed, while others cannot. Therefore, the adequacy of this exercise for this purpose can be assessed as minimal.

The process of forming a grammatical skill includes the following stages: perception, imitation, substitution, transformation, combination. What does a lookup table contribute? The perception in it is not auditory, but visual, that is, not adequate to speaking.

The action of substitution is carried out, but it is not speech in nature. There are no other actions - transformation and others at all, that is, for other stages the substitution table has zero adequacy.

It is also necessary to take into account factors in the organization of exercises. After all, you can give a speech instruction (a speech task will appear), use illustrative clarity (conditional situationality will appear), use a tape recorder (auditory support will appear), etc. Thus, the adequacy of the substitution table immediately increases: it becomes maximally adequate for the stages of perception, imitation and substitution.

Consequently, the same exercise in different conditions, at different stages of work, differently organized, can be adequate to the goal to varying degrees. To summarize all that has been said, we note that the task of a teacher teaching children the Russian language is to organize teaching on the basis of a strict grammatical system, the study of which at the same time would not be an end in itself for the student, but would be recognized as a necessary condition for understanding in communication process. The teacher must, by skillfully selecting exercises for active mastery of grammar, lead the student to full mastery of Russian speech.

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